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1. TITLE Assessment of the Training Needs of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials and Members and of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Erwin D. Naval¹
Ernest Esmeralda¹
Diwata Donato¹
Niña Rheena Salinas¹
Jones K. Liwan¹

¹ Faculty Member of Department of Social Sciences and Philosophy

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2. ABSTRACT

Youth participation in governance is an investment of every nation. RA 7160 created the SK and KK as primary youth organizations mandated to work for reforms, policies, and projects. After three decades, the KK and SK have been blemished with issues such as corruption, political dynasty, mismanagement, skills deficiencies, and incompetence. In 2016, RA 10742 introduced the capacitation of the SK officials with training and seminars to enhance their skills and competencies. The study assessed the training needs of 116 KK members and SK officials of the municipality of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, by determining their knowledge and competencies. This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative type of research. Results of the study show that respondents have a fair knowledge of the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization, and local governance, while poor on Parliamentary Procedures. They have low competencies in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning, and fostering collaboration among the youth. Results show significant differences in their knowledge of the Code of Ethics and Standards, decentralization and local governance, and Parliamentary Procedures, including their competencies in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, planning, and effective communication. Findings imply that the respondents have weak capacities in managing the KK and SK. Their limited capacities for strategic thinking, policy development, planning, and implementation, engaging other youth, as well as partnership, suggest for a training program that will capacitate and enhance fundamental skills of KK members and SK officials essential in organizational management and legislation.

Keywords: knowledge, competencies, local legislation, parliamentary procedures, policy development, project execution.

3. INTRODUCTION

The world now recognizes the direct participation of the youth in governance. Every nation invests in youth development because the youth are the world's future. This is consistent with Dr. Jose Rizal, the Filipino national hero writing that youth are the true hope of the fatherland. However, developing young people toward nation-building is a process. In the Philippines, as early as 1975, Filipinos aged fifteen to eighteen participated in governance. Presidential Decree number 684

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created Kabataang Barangay (KB), originally to strengthen the role of the youth in every barangay. It also provided an avenue for a more democratic legislative process for reforms aspired by the youth. Balanon et al. (2007) reported that during the early 1980s, the KB became less popular, and the youth turned to activism.

In 1991, RA 7160 abolished the KB and created the Katipunan ng Kabataan (KK) and Sangguniang Kabataan (SK). It recognizes the youth's role in nation-building and active participation in governance. It mandates the SK to promulgate resolutions and initiate programs and fund-raising activities. Hence, KK members and SK officials are essentially expected to develop legislative competencies in doing this mandate. In 2016, RA 10742 stipulated that the KK serves as the highest policy-making body on all matters affecting the youth in the Barangay. It mandates SK to legislate policies and programs of action into resolutions and ordinances to carry out meaningful programs and projects.

However, legislation and program development as political exercises are not easy because these involve too much bickering among politicians (Guinid, 2018). Twenty years after creating the SK, there were calls to abolish it because of corruption breeding, political dynasty, mismanagement, skills deficiencies, and incompetence. Balanon et al., (2007) found that SK taught essential skills and values to Filipino youth and provided beneficial opportunities. However, there are rampant practices of corruption and nepotism among SK councils. Malaluan et al., (2014); Balanon et al., (2007) reported that SK's performance, particularly in legislating resolutions and ordinances, submitting reports, and holding consultations with its constituents, is generally weak. Flores et al., (2022) documented that the SK system undermines youth development in the country because it is marred with corruption, political patronage, inefficient systems, and tokenistic programs. The many issues surrounding the SK created the clamor for its abolition. That is why in 2016, congress enacted RA 10742 to institute reforms in the SK, such as the capacitation of its officials as legislators designing resolutions, addressing youth concerns, including managing projects, programs, and finance. After six years, have the KK and SK officials transformed into better legislators and youth leaders? What government interventions are being implemented to transform them into better legislators and leaders?

The study assessed the training needs of SK officials and KK members of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, by determining their skills, knowledge, and competencies. Specifically, this study determined the respondents' (1) training on leadership and decision-making, local legislation, financial management and budgeting, and project execution; (2) level of knowledge on the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization and local governance, and Parliamentary Procedures; (3) the level of competencies on effective decision making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration for the youth, and effective communication; and (4) the differences on their knowledge and competencies when grouped according to profile variables.

4. METHODOLOGY

This quantitative type of research utilized a descriptive-comparative methodology. In this approach, data about training, knowledge, and competencies were gathered using questionnaires. These training include leadership and decision-making, local legislation, financial management and budgeting, and project execution, which are geared towards strengthening and empowering the youth as a helpful actors in community development, civic affairs, and effective participation in local governance. Aside from training, this research determined the respondents' knowledge, particularly

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on the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization and local governance, and parliamentary procedures. These manifest their cognition of commitment, accountability, responsibility, integrity, competence, and loyalty in performing their duties. Furthermore, this study also determined the competencies manifested by the abilities to navigate through the process of evaluating solutions towards a decision, assess internal and external realities and risks, formulate relevant policy initiatives and recommendations, develop and formulate plans, facilitate involvement and engagement of youth, and use appropriate language and approaches in providing information to stakeholders.

The study was conducted at the Municipality of Bayombong. It can be located in the northern part of Luzon. It is a first-class municipality and the capital of the province of Nueva Vizcaya. The Dominican friars formally organized the municipality in 1739. According to the 2020 Census, it has a population of 67,714. Bayombong is politically subdivided into 25 Barangays which elected barangay officials manage. Each Barangay has an organized KK comprising youth members aged 15 -30 years old, and the SK comprises an elected chairman and 7 Kagawad, including an appointed secretary and treasurer.

The respondents of the study were the purposively selected KK members and SK officials of the 25 barangays of Bayombong. The SK officials included the chairman and Kagawad, elected during the 2018 SK Election, including the appointed secretary and treasurer. The KK members and SK officials selected were in the age bracket of 18-30 years old. There were no respondents below 18 years old. The SK officials who are currently overseas and resigned from their positions were excluded. There were 116 respondents who participated in the study.

This study used questionnaires to gather data needed to answer the research problems. The questionnaires have three parts – training experience, knowledge, and competencies of the KK members and SK Officials. Many of the items were adopted from the Guidebook on the Competency Framework for the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Officials and Local Youth Development Officers (LYDOs) of DILG. The first part asked about training experiences of the SK officials' leadership and decision-making, local legislation, financial management and budgeting, and project execution. Meanwhile, the second part determined the level of knowledge of the respondents on the Code of conduct and ethical standards, decentralization and local governance, and Parliamentary procedures. The third part determined the level of competencies of SK officials in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration for the youth, and effective communication.

The researchers requested a copy of the list of KK members and elected SK officials from the Municipal Local Government Office of Bayombong located at the Local Government Unit building. There were 200 selected respondents from the 25 barangays who were active members of the KK and incumbent officials of the SK. An informed consent form was given to them that contains the nature of the study. Respondents were given the freedom to decide if they were willing to participate in the study. Some respondents refused to be part of the study. Those who signed the consent forms signified their willingness and answered the questionnaires. The researchers collected the questionnaires after answering. Data gathered from the respondents were treated with the utmost confidentiality and used solely for research purposes. The data was only accessed and processed by the researchers. The answered questionnaires were disposed of properly after the conduct of the study, while the dataset file was deleted after the conduct of the study.

The quantitative data were tabulated using the SPSS. Descriptive Statistics, particularly frequencies, Means, and Standard Deviations, were used in analyzing the level of knowledge of the respondents on the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization and local governance, and Parliamentary Procedures. Furthermore, Descriptive Statistics were also used in determining

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the level of competencies in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration, and effective communication. Differences in the knowledge and competencies of respondents were analyzed using T-Test.

5. RESULTS

One of the objectives of this research was to determine the seminars and training attended by the KK members and SK officials. In terms of seminars and training on leadership and decision-making attended, the respondents listed DILG Mandatory Trainings, Youth Leadership Seminar, NSTP Leadership Seminar, Youth Camp, and SK Team Building. There were only two on local legislation written by the respondents, which include Young Provincial Official Seminar and DILG Sponsored Trainings and Seminars. Aside from these, there were also seminars and training regarding financial management, which included DILG and COA-sponsored Financial Management Seminar and Training-Workshop on Planning and Budgeting. Lastly, the respondents said they had no seminars or training on Project Execution during their term as KK members and SK officials.

Results of the survey show that the overall level of knowledge of the respondents on the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards is fair. The respondents fairly know how to act with justness and sincerity in order not to discriminate against anyone, especially the poor and the underprivileged, and also in their actions which are non-discriminatory to any party affiliation or preference. In addition, they fairly know how to extend prompt, courteous, and adequate service to the public. On the other hand, the respondents' levels of knowledge in upholding the SK resources and use of powers for efficient, effective, honest, and economical management and discouraging wrong perceptions of their roles as leaders of political patronage are poor.

In terms of decentralization and local governance, the level of knowledge of the respondents is generally fair. Respondents fairly know how to maximize the formal and informal networks to expedite actions and decisions for the youth development programs as well as in complying consistently with the national and local government's regulations, rules, and policies, including adopting the best practices in governance. Similarly, the respondents fairly know how to act with rationality and accountability in their decisions and management operations of the SK organization. Moreover, the results of the study show that the respondents have poor knowledge of administrative issuances of COA, DBM, DILG, and the Local Chief Executive of the municipality, and unspoken organizational limitations or dos and don'ts of their position.

Findings reveal that there is a poor overall level of knowledge of respondents on Parliamentary Procedures (Mean= 2.58, SD= .90432). They have fair knowledge, skill, and background in taking the privilege of speaking in an assembly and in recognizing the privileges and rights of other members in connection with matters of physical comfort, ineligibility, or misconduct of a member in a meeting. Similarly, their knowledge of guiding or orienting other youth in understanding the formal structures, policies, and mandates surrounding youth development is also at a fair level. However, the results also show that KK members and leaders have poor knowledge, skill, and background in observing the order of business set in a meeting or session, in voting for or against an issue or motion raised, and in the use of appropriate motions to propose or oppose an action or decision of the assembly.

The survey shows that the overall level of competency in effective decision-making (Mean= 2.58, SD= .8985) of respondents is low. Specifically, the respondents have low competencies in making decisions unilaterally and communicating during urgent or sensitive situations, providing sound solutions from available options regarding youth issues and concerns, and choosing the most suitable decision based on evidence. Results of the study further revealed that the respondents have

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no ability to explain and recommend action based on the evaluation of the request, inquiry, or issue at hand, even in evaluating the impact of their decision as well as in modifying the course of action as needed, and in the consultation of the team members for inputs or decision making.

Meanwhile, the results of the study show the respondents' overall level of competency in strategic thinking (Mean= 2.96, SD= 1.08037) is low. They have low levels of abilities and skills in recognizing points of improvement, developing interventions or new programs, generating or suggesting ideas and courses of action, developing strategies to cope with changing environments and challenges, and engaging others to develop new insights, including formulating creative solutions. In addition, their competencies of anticipating potential threats and opportunities to reduce risk and other possible future consequences and looking beyond the immediate situation as well as considering the long-term impact and consequences of current activities of the SK organization, are also low.

In terms of policy development, the respondents have a low level of competencies (Mean= 2.81, SD=.99619). The survey results show that respondents need occasional supervision in applying specialized knowledge to policy formulation, developing policy initiatives and recommendations, and drafting papers according to policy guidelines. The data also reveal that KK members and SK officials have low levels of competencies in creating, monitoring, implementing, and evaluating frameworks that incorporate standards and risk management, and impact analysis of projects. They also have low competencies in reviewing research and studies assessing effective and relevant policies and soliciting feedback from program implementers.

The respondents' overall level of competency in planning for results (Mean=2.89, SD=.98458) is low. Results of the survey show that the respondents have a low level of abilities in effective management of time in accomplishing their plans, setting daily or priority targets and goals within a reasonable time, progress monitoring of tasks and activities, designing activities or interventions with partners, recommending a project progress monitoring system, and use tools to plan and organize time effectively.

In terms of the ability to foster collaboration for the youth, the respondents' overall level of competency (Mean= 2.97, SD= 1.0303) is low. Specifically, they need occasional supervision on convening youth volunteers during consultations and discussions, persuading youth for activities and visioning, and engaging fellow members of KK in discussions about youth concerns and issues. Results also reveal that the respondents need occasional supervision because they have low abilities on collaborating in youth activities and projects, carrying out actions and agreements of partners and volunteers, and winning the trust of other youth.

Survey results of the study show that respondents' overall level of competency in effective communication (Mean= 3.09, SD= .96461) is low. Results of the survey reveal that they have low abilities to express their ideas effectively using oral and written means of communication, actively listening to stakeholders and partners during consultations, leading the conduct of meetings or small group discussions, organizing thoughts and ideas effectively, creating a safe office environment for open and inclusive communication, and setting agenda during assembly meetings. However, it can be gleaned from the results that the respondents have a moderate competency level in encouraging others to voice out their concerns, opinions, and suggestions, including recognizing and respecting individual differences toward mutual agreement and order.

Another objective of this study is to determine significant differences in the level of knowledge of the respondents regarding Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization and local governance, and Parliamentary Procedures. The following are the results.

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Table 1

Differences in knowledge on Code of conduct and ethical standards, decentralization and local governance, and parliamentary procedures when respondents are grouped according to Barangay classifications.

	Classification of Barangay	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Code of conduct and ethical standards	Urbanized Barangay	58	3.28	1.0509	2	103	.019*
	Rural Barangay	58	2.88	.7473			
Decentralization and local governance	Urbanized Barangay	58	2.93	1.0658	2	105	.040*
	Rural Barangay	58	2.56	.7951			
Parliamentary procedures	Urbanized Barangay	58	2.82	1.0707	1	109	.204
	Rural Barangay	58	2.59	.8562			

*Reject Ho if p value is $\leq .05$

Table 1 shows that there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge of respondents on Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards as well as in decentralization and local governance when they are grouped according to their Barangay classifications.

Furthermore, when respondents are grouped according to their positions, there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge on the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization, and local governance, including Parliamentary procedures. Results also show that there is no significant difference in their level of knowledge of Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards when the respondents are grouped according to sex.

The Statistical results also show that there are no significant differences in the respondents' competencies in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration for the youth, and effective communication when respondents are grouped according to Barangay classifications and sex variables.

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Table 2

Differences in competencies on effective decision making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration for the youth, and effective communication when respondents are grouped according to positions.

	SK Position	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Effective decision making	SK Official	25	3.94	.98621	9.130	114	.000*
	KK Member	91	2.38	.68406			
Strategic thinking	SK Official	25	4.08	.74087	7.07	51.72	.000*
	KK Member	91	2.79	1.01928			
Policy development	SK Official	25	3.59	1.21438	3.27	31.86	.003*
	KK Member	91	2.74	.91495			
Planning for results	SK Official	25	3.80	.88192	4.98	114	.000*
	KK Member	91	2.76	.93097			
Fostering collaboration for the youth	SK Official	25	3.93	.92045	5.18	114	.000*
	KK Member	91	2.82	.95496			
Effective communication	SK Official	25	4.00	.95876	5.31	114	.000*
	KK Member	91	2.94	.85320			

*Reject Ho if p value is ≤ .05

Moreover, Statistical results shown in Table 2 reveal that there are significant differences in the respondents' competencies in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration for the youth, and effective communication when they are grouped according to positions.

6. DISCUSSIONS

The respondents fairly know the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards. This implies that members of the KK in the municipality of Bayombong have a deficiency of seminars and trainings on good governance intended to develop young leaders in managing effective, efficient, and economical resources compared to SK officials who have a number of trainings and seminars. The respondents reveal that KK members are not given seminars and trainings to improve their knowledge which reduces their propensity to promote political patronage. Most of the trainings were given to SK officials, especially the chairman. This is consistent with the study of Cal et al. (2023) on the effectiveness of SK Mandatory Training conducted for the SK Officials of selected barangays of Cebu City, which confirmed that the SK Officials are very knowledgeable at the same time demonstrated high knowledge on Decentralization and Local Governance, SK History, Meetings, and Resolutions, Planning and Budgeting, Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards after the mandatory seminars conducted by DILG.

Moreover, KK members and SK officials in the municipality have poor knowledge of administrative issuances of COA, DBM, DILG, and the Local Chief Executive, as well as in complying

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with unspoken organizational limitations. These findings suggest that there are limited trainings and seminars aimed at enhancing the knowledge and awareness of the youth and their leaders regarding existing and new policies stipulated in administrative COA, DBM, DILG, and LCE issuances and orders regarding youth affairs in the municipality of Bayombong. This implies that some of their decisions and actions in the management of the SK organization activities, funding, projects, etc., are in non-compliance with specific issuances and regulations.

KK members and leaders also show deficient knowledge of Parliamentary Procedures, specifically in observing the order of business, voting procedures, and the proper use of motions in the assembly. These findings suggest that there is scarce training on local legislation processes and parliamentary rules and procedures for members of the KK and SK officials. Responses from the survey respondents show that the SK chairmen were given many of the trainings on local legislation process and Parliamentary Procedures. This is consistent with Libo-on (2020) and Guinid (2020) findings that the knowledge of parliamentary rules and procedures of SK officials in the actual demonstration of skills is average only, most especially in setting the order of business and in the handling of motions. Their study also reported SK chairman has only basic knowledge and skills in parliamentary rules and procedures. However, many of these trainings were not given to other SK officials and KK members. A significant difference was also seen in the respondents' level of knowledge of the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards, decentralization, and local governance, including Parliamentary procedures. The SK Chairman is usually given the opportunities for trainings and seminars. Hence, many SK officials and KK members are incapacitated in local legislation processes and parliamentary procedures, which supposedly make them better legislators and leaders of the youth.

Aside from knowledge, the respondents' competency in effective decision-making is low. This implies many of the members of the KK, as well as officials of the SK, have a low level of capacity decision-making, particularly in communicating decisions during urgent and sensitive situations. These findings also suggest that many of them have no background, knowledge, or skill in making rational organizational decisions. Thus, many of their decisions are not collectively made or analyzed and are often baseless. Therefore, they need capacitation seminars in analytical decision-making and developing evidence-based solutions.

The KK members and SK officials have revealed that they have no competencies in explaining and recommending action based on the evaluation of the issue at hand, even in impact evaluation of their decision and action, including in consulting the team members for inputs on the decision-making. They admitted they require maximum supervision in the scientific evaluation of decisions and actions as well as in team dynamics for decision-making. This suggests the KK members and SK officials need to undergo full training, which would teach them strategies for impact evaluation of their organizational decisions, including action, and consequently help in managing team dynamics.

Many of the respondents admitted they have weak strategic thinking abilities and skills, particularly in developing new programs, developing strategies contributory to their organizational future, and formulating new insights and creative solutions. The members of the KK and officials of the SK need occasional supervision in anticipating potential threats and opportunities, as well as considering long-term impact and consequences. Hence, trainings on strategic organizational thinking and actions will capacitate them. These additional trainings will enhance their ability to take a broad-scale approach in assessing internal and external youth realities and risks as well as in considering consequences, implications, interdependencies, and indirect long and short-term effects on youth concerns.

The respondents also show deficient policy development abilities, which means they need occasional supervision in technicalities of policy formulation, policy evaluation, and project

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monitoring and implementation. These findings suggest that the KK members and SK officials are limitedly capacitated with the ability to formulate, develop, present, and finalize relevant policy initiatives and recommendations. They need trainings and seminars to develop functional competencies in reviewing researches and studies assessing effective and relevant policies helpful in policies and programs management.

In terms of planning for results, KK members and SK officials in the municipality have limited abilities and skills. Hence, they need occasional supervision in planning, most especially in effective management of time in accomplishing their plans and setting priority targets and goals. In order that their SK organizations will develop administrative efficacy, they need rigorous trainings on project progress monitoring systems, development partnerships, planning controls, and activity management tools.

Furthermore, KK members and SK officials in the municipality manifest weak abilities to foster collaboration. They have experienced difficulties in convening youth volunteers, persuading their fellow youth to create a vision, and engaging in forums discussing concerns and issues, forging collaboration for projects, actions, and agreements. These findings suggest that the SK officials and KK members in the municipality need capacitation in fostering collaboration among the youth. These also imply that they need additional trainings to enhance skills and abilities of involving and engaging their fellow youth members, leaders, and volunteers in youth-related activities which are collective, inclusive, and harmonious manner.

The results of the study also show that the communication competency of the respondents is weak. Findings suggest that SK officials and KK members need additional trainings to enhance their ability to communicate spoken and written means and in providing information to and from internal and external stakeholders. Many of them need trainings and seminars to enhance their oral and written abilities to effectively express their ideas as officials and youth members. Capacitation seminars would transform them into active listeners of stakeholders and partners, leaders in the conduct of meetings or small group discussions with effective and organized thoughts and ideas, and creators of a safe atmosphere for open communication. The results also showed that the respondents have a moderate competency level in encouraging others to voice concerns, opinions, and suggestions, including the recognition and respect of individual differences toward mutual agreement and order. Almonte et al.(2015) documented that SK officials and KK members have effectively used café dialogue as the communication process, which helped them better in discussions. The informal and comfortable discussions allowed them effectively in making solutions without limitations for their youth organization. This implies that they have working knowledge and skills to express themselves as well as recognizing and respecting individual differences thereby, they need minimal supervision, but they still need occasional refresher interventions.

Significant differences were seen in the respondents' competencies in effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration for the youth, and effective communication between KK members and SK officials. This is also a result of the practice that SK chairmen with few SK Kagawad were mostly sent for trainings and seminars. Consequently, there are few SK officials capacitated with fundamental competencies.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Members of the KK and SK in the municipality of Bayombong have weak knowledge of good governance, particularly in managing effective, efficient, and economic resources of the government. Their knowledge of parliamentary procedures and policymaking used in local legislation as well as the application of COA, DBM, DILG, and LCE issuances to their activities and decision making, are

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insufficient. Hence, seminars and trainings on good governance and parliamentary procedures are the top-most priorities to improve their knowledge as better youth leaders. In terms of competencies, there is an absence of abilities to evaluate the impacts of decisions made among the SK officials. They have limited capacities for strategic thinking used in taking a broad-scale approach to assess internal and external youth realities and organizational risks, even in the abilities to formulate, develop, present, and finalize relevant policy initiatives and recommendations. Members of the KK and officials of the SK have inadequate capacities to manage their action plans, conduct progress reports, collaborate with partners, monitoring processes in their projects. There are inadequate abilities of SK officials to convene volunteers, engage other youth, as well as making agreements for partnership. Their oral and written communication, most especially in gathering meetings and listening to stakeholders are insufficient. However, they have enough competencies to voice out concerns, opinions, and suggestions, as well as to maintain respect for individual differences. Consequently, there is a need for strategic interventions to improve the individual

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

The LGU of Bayombong should design an engaging training program on local legislation, parliamentary procedures, and good governance for the youth in the municipality. The MLGO creates regular information dissemination seminars and forums to update members of the KK and SK officials regarding new and existing COA, DBM, DILG, and LCE issuances regarding the management of their organization. There should be sustained partnerships among LGU, NGOs, and academe in capacity building on developing policy initiatives, project management and evaluation, forging partnerships, and communication for the youth. SK Federation in partnership with MLGO, and Saint Mary's University to design capacitation seminars and trainings that will develop fundamental competencies of the youth on effective decision-making, strategic thinking, policy development, planning for results, fostering collaboration, and effective communication. Finally, the creation of the Strategic Interventions in Building Outstanding Leaders (Project SIBOL) of the SK and KK.

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